

REVIEWS FROM SELECTED ONLINE TRAVEL AGENCIES ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN HOTEL LUNA, VIGAN CITY

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Abstract: In the hotel industry, hotels are making ways to be a unique one and stand amongst others. Customer satisfaction is considered as an important factor in order to evaluate a hotel's performance. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze the reviews from selected online travel agencies on customer satisfaction in Hotel Luna, Vigan City based on the SERVQUAL theory in terms of the following variables: Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy. This research will provide further data on the hotel to improve their services if needed. This research utilized a qualitative research design specifically sentiment analysis. Non-probability purposive sampling will also be used in order to collect data for the study which will be gathered in Microsoft Excel. The researchers will measure the data using a five-point Likert scale.

Keywords: SERVQUAL, online travel agencies, customer satisfaction, Hotel Luna.

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer Satisfaction is a reflection on how a customer feels about a company. It simply measures how the customer's standards are met by the company's quality service and must be prioritized by any kind of business (Razaka et al., 2019). Since customers are considered as a significant asset for a company, their viewpoints are essential and must be asked out on a regular basis (Aimee, 2019). According to Li, et al., (2020), it is given that customer satisfaction is such an important way to evaluate a hotel's performance, operators must also have a detailed understanding of the aspects that lead to both satisfied and dissatisfied guests. If the services by the hotel are pleasing, guests will be more likely to return and recommend the hotel to others. Satisfaction is the main reason people come to visit destinations such as hotels and it also determines the quality of the location (Atabeb, 2019). On the other hand, if the services by the hotel are disappointing, guests will be more prone to spread unenthusiastic word of mouth, which will become the reason for the hotel's reputation to reduce revenues by preventing new customers (Li et al., 2020).

According to Davras et al., (2019) satisfied customers will purchase more or repeat from the company which makes them loyal since they trust the company or business. Customer loyalty can be seen as a vital element in gaining competitive advantage over other companies (Leninkumar et al., 2017). Through evaluating the customer's satisfaction, tourism businesses under the same sector will be in a better state to understand how their service and performance is

perceived by customers and to be able to clearly see the areas that need improvement (Hamzah et al., 2020). The concept of service quality and customer satisfaction must understand by an organization if they want to stay competitive and profitable (Davras et al., 2019).

The Historic Town of Vigan, with its historical checkerboard street design, is Asia's greatest illustration of a planned Spanish colonial town (worldheritagesite.org). Vigan is regarded as a one-of-a-kind destination due to its preserved Spanish historical heritage, particularly the grid street structure and traditional urban structure, and as a result, the number of visitors is constantly increasing (whc.unesco.org). One of the well-known hotels located in Vigan is the Hotel Luna. In fact, it is considered the best hotel in Vigan near Calle Crisologo, with Heritage & Rustic Style (Muzones, 2018). It is the Philippines' first and only certified museum hotel with the ambiance of Spanish era and its location in the historical city of Vigan (Victa, 2016). According to Traveloka PH, (2018) Although the Hotel Luna is an attraction in itself, it is also ideally positioned to be close to Vigan's most popular tourist attractions. The property is only one block away from Calle Crisologo. According to (Galiste, 2018) the city of Vigan received 1.4 million tourist arrivals from year 2017, including local and international tourist who visiting a well-known heritage city of Vigan according to figures from the municipality tourism office. This record shows that Vigan is famous for tourists not only because of its art, design, and architecture, but also because of its history and education. Lucena (2015) mentioned that since the Spanish period, Vigan has also been home to a lot of ancestral homes that have been transformed into museums which display historical archives and artifacts.

According to a recent study (Talwar et al., 2020) travelers are increasingly aiming to create their itineraries and tour programs that do not include high-cost lodgings and booking arrangements. As a result, online platforms that enables people to do such things have risen in popularity. Websites of online travel agencies (OTAs) contribute towards introducing new clients to hotels (Chang et al., 2019). They also mentioned that online travel agencies (OTAs) can allure new and repeat guests by improving the quality of the website's service. Therefore, any internet user recognizes the ability to create their own itineraries with the help of digital tools that regularly allows tourists to directly book accommodation from a wide range of options at listed locations (Ayo et al., 2020). The use of online travel agency websites is still on the rise despite all of the economic issues but there may be a reduction of travel opportunities due to the pandemic. However, once the pandemic is gone, the use of online travel agencies will still be prioritized because of convenience (Monterey et al., 2021). Most of the well-known online travel agencies in the Philippines are TripAdvisor, and Agoda. The mentioned platforms use customer ratings as a source of knowledge to assist other customers who are making travel plans (Borges-Tiago et al., 2021).

According to (TripAdvisor, 2019) Every month, 463 million travelers use the world's leading travel website, which is TripAdvisor, to make every journey their best trip. Over 8.6 million lodgings, restaurants, activities, airlines, and cruises are available on the TripAdvisor website and app, that can be used by travelers all over the world (TripAdvisor, 2019). Tourists can leave reviews on TripAdvisor about their hotel experiences. The hotel's reputation and image can be created by the written review, as well as a challenge to provide the best service. Tourists' decision to stay at the hotel will be influenced by this (Sumarsono et al., 2019). On the other hand, Agoda, as a component of the online travel agents (OTA) industry, provides not only products but also services through its e-commerce (Wachyuni et al., 2020). Based on (Agoda, 2019) Agoda has expanded since its establishment as an e-commerce start-up in Singapore in 2005, it has grown to a global network of 2 million properties in over 200 countries. Both of the mentioned online travel agencies are available in different languages and markets.

This study conducted to analyze the reviews on customer satisfaction in the Hotel Luna, Vigan City based on the SERVQUAL theory in terms of the following variables: Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy. Therefore, to fill the gap, this research provided further organized information through the evaluation and reviews in the selected online travel agencies. This research provided further information to students, professionals, and officers to have a better understanding of the Hotel Luna under the tourism industry. This research would be beneficial to the future travelers because after analyzing the data, the Hotel Luna can improve their services. In this study, the hotel management would also benefit on this study because they will be aware of the services and facilities that Hotel Luna can improve based on research. This research would also be beneficial to future researchers because they can gather information that might be needed in their research and some of their question may possibly be answered by this research. The research will be conducted in Hotel Luna Vigan City, Ilocos Sur Philippines through the most well-known online travel agency TripAdvisor and Agoda website.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In a study by Tabaku et al., (2016), using the SERVPERF theory within 5-Likert scale framework is used to collect the tourist opinion to determine the service quality as well as customer satisfaction. This study aimed to provide an evaluation of the service quality provided by the hotel along Albanian coast, as well as the impact of service quality on hotel customer satisfaction. The findings of statistical analyses of obtained data demonstrate the tourists' views of the service quality are extremely important, and that recognized service quality has a considerable effect on customer satisfaction for hotel guests. However, the conceptual model did not fit the research topic because it is based on performance approach to the measurement of service quality.

In a study by Li et al., (2020), a Dempster-Shafer evidence theory was used as a tool for measuring hotel customer satisfaction which was considered as a reliability for online review section and data from online travel agencies. The theory was made of three stages. First, the general probability is derived based on reviews online, considering differences in dependability of reviews online. Following that, the data from evaluation is compiled using the entropy weight method and Dempster's rule of combination. Lastly, the expected utility is determined using the value function, and customer satisfaction is assessed using the expected value that is calculated. As a result, customer satisfaction improvement plans were designed based on customer satisfaction rankings.

However, the conceptual theory did not fit the research topic because it evaluates sets of propositions rather than single propositions and provides an interval to each set within which the set's degree of belief must fit and often referred to as a probability theory extension.

Puri & Singh (2019), service quality and customer satisfaction models' existing literature was reviewed in this study. The management were encouraged to improve its services to satisfy the guests and applied the dimension model in the tourism industry. Based on the findings, customer satisfaction is a necessary antecedent of service quality, and satisfaction makes major contribution of service quality and behavioral intention. A similar study conducted by Buena (2020), the study used two frameworks. First is the Uncertainty Reduction Theory, which is a well-known customer-to-customer communication theory that has been used as a theoretical foundation for scientific studies into the elements that can change customers' trust in online reviews. Second one is Cognitive Dissonance Theory, as basic concepts that were tested with series of quantitative data and analysis to develop a model that expounds the primary phenomena of the data collected. The findings can be seen in the theory of this study, The data presented in the context of this study, and after testing and identifying the links among the factors, a model for resorts to boost consumer trust and offset cognitive dissonance toward internet reviews was developed.

In a study by Li et al., (2020), In accordance with distinct hotel star ratings and consumer segments, the research aimed to determine how the purpose of the hotel relates to basic, excitement, and performance, as well as how they differ. However, the study used the three-factor theory which does not relate to the research topic. Product or services characteristics have asymmetric influence on overall customer satisfaction and basic, performance, and excitement factors are three types of hotel attribute factor, according to the three-type theory.

Figure 1

SERVQUAL Theory

- **Reliability:** This indicates that the service company provides customers with reliable and excellent service from the start and does that within the time frame given (Al-Ababneh, 2016)
- **Assurance:** This indicates the staff's actions can provide customers with a sense of security and trust in the organization. Employees, on the other hand, are always friendly and able to answer queries from customers (Al-Ababneh, 2016).
- **Tangibility:** This indicates the pleasure and satisfaction of the surroundings. Physical equipment, infrastructure, personnel, and other aspects of a company's tools for communication. In addition to this, tangibility involves the appearance of the staff (Al-Ababneh, 2016).
- **Empathy:** This indicates the employee's ability to interpret a customer's concerns, act in their best interests, and treat them as persons. Empathy also entails ensuring the company's hours of operation are appropriate (Al-Ababneh, 2016).
- **Responsiveness:** This indicates the employees' willingness to work, to assist customers and answer their questions with a quick response (Al-Ababneh, 2016).

The previous contrast research with different framework leads researchers to use SERVQUAL Theory. In 1988, Parasuraman et al., marketing gurus from the United States, designed and implemented the SERVQUAL Model, which is a way of measuring and evaluating consumer satisfaction with service. In a study conducted by Wang et al., (2015) every industry can use the SERVQUAL Model as a full rating system to help their management gain credibility and efficiency, as well as to improve their service quality. Therefore, SERVQUAL has proven to be a successful model in the tourism industry, where various key studies and research have demonstrated that in different regions of the world, the SERVQUAL model has been effective (Mihaela, 2014). The perception gap is the foundation of SERVQUAL that has been commonly used to explain the difference between the quality of the service obtained and the quality of the service expected (Ravichandran et al., 2010). Ten dimensions of service quality were originally created which includes of Reliability, Responsiveness, Competence, Access, Courtesy, Communication, Credibility, Security, Understanding the consumer, and Tangibles. These were later reduced to five (Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, Assurances and Tangibles) which is also known as RATER Model (Ravichandran et al., 2010). In this case, the researchers will utilize this model since it examines both the customer's expectations and views of the service which makes it the most accurate technique to assess the service quality of the business.

According to a study by Mañas et al. (2018), SERVQUAL model by Parasuraman were used to understand the significance relationship of employee motivation and customer satisfaction. Employees were encouraged to provide quality service in order to have a satisfactory service. According to the findings, the SERVQUAL Theory was helpful in order for the researchers to analyze if the hotel had a high degree of motivation and client satisfaction. However, no significant differences or connections were discovered in the study's findings. For Monterey and Borbon (2021), The SERVQUAL model was used in service quality of online travel agencies in CALABARZON. In order to propose a framework of innovation for the online travel agency, The OTA's service performance in terms of client satisfaction was studied in order to suggest an innovation framework for the online travel agency.

Based on a study by Ali et al. (2021), in quest for long-term competitive advantage, service quality has identified as a significant component by satisfying and the retaining the customer for being the most important factor in hospitality industry. The major goal of this study found out how service quality affects customers' satisfaction. The study's findings demonstrated the impact of several SERVQUAL parameters on hotel satisfaction levels. Sharma & Srivastava (2018), SERVQUAL model by Parasuraman was used which will eventually conduct them to extemporize their customer services. In the competitive hotel industry in the whole world, each of all individual hotels find their own way to make their products and services unique and identifying on how they will shine amongst others. The study also investigated into whether SERVQUAL model can help hotels satisfy their customers.

Gumussoy & Koseoglu (2016), SERVQUAL was measured with this study multiple dimensions and each dimension influenced the overall assessment of service quality from the customers' viewpoint. The goal of their research is to discover the factors that influence hotel customers' satisfaction and loyalty. In order to describe customer satisfaction, a study model was constructed that includes service quality, perceived pricing fairness, and perceived value, loyalty, and satisfaction.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researchers will use the qualitative research design specifically sentiment analysis. According to Hennink et al., (2020) using a specific set of research methods, qualitative research allows you to analyze people's experiences in depth. Based in a study by Aspers et al., (2019), the advantage of using qualitative research is to assist the improvement of research designs and also assist with studies, communication within researchers, bridging the gap between qualitative and quantitative researchers, addressing review of qualitative methodologies, and serving as a standard for qualitative research evaluation. On the other hand, Sentiment Analysis is a text classification technique that categorizes texts according to the sentiment orientation of opinions included within them. It determines whether the data gathered is positive, negative, or neutral (Devika et al., 2016). Therefore, the researchers will use Sentiment Analysis in the study because it can process the categorizing documents as positive or negative, based on their overall conveyed opinion or known as reviews (Markopoulos et al., 2015). Sentiment analysis uses a variety of spoken language processing and text processing methods to do a computational analysis of attitudes and views represented in text.

The researchers will use a non-probability purposive sampling in order to collect data for the study. In a study of Rai et al., (2015), the purposive sampling refers to the process of selecting observations from a population to be included in a sample survey. It is also an easy and low-cost way to gather data. The researchers will analyze and will gather data by analyzing all the reviews from year 2016 to 2022 which will come from the selected online travel agencies with a total of 720 reviews. Specific categories will be used, it consists of five factors which includes Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy which was discussed in the previous pages.

Table 1: Summary of study units to be examined

Online Travel Agencies	Online Travel Agency reviews links	No. of reviews
Tripadvisor	https://www.tripadvisor.com.ph/Hotel_Review-g424958-d6429034-Reviews-Hotel_LunaVigan_Ilocos_Sur_Province_Ilocos_Region_Luzon.html#REVIEWS	360
Agoda	https://www.agoda.com/hotel-luna_3/hotel/ilocos-sur-ph.html?finalPriceView=1&isShowMobileAppPrice=false&cid=1844104&numberOfBedrooms=&familyMode=false&adults=2&children=0&rooms=1&maxRooms=0&checkIn=2022-02-6&isCalendarCallout=false&childAges=&numberOfGuest=0&missingChildAges=false&travellerType=1&showReviewSubmissionEntry=false&currencyCode=PHP&isFreeOccSearch=false&isCityHaveA sq=false&isDayUseFunnel=false&tpTypes=4,8&los=1&searchrequestid=6978a4f4-33a2-4a1b-a50e-aedd5c8b99c2	360
		Total: 720

The data will be gathered using Microsoft Excel. A Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet organizes data in a comprehensible format, making it easier for researchers to extract information. When working with more intricate data, Microsoft Excel allows users to edit fields and functions that conduct computations (Khandavilli, 2021). It also makes cooperation simple and allows numerous people to work together. The data will be gathered using the Pivot table in Microsoft Excel. It can sort, show, analyze, and examine the summary of data. A Pivot Table can be used to study numerical data in depth and to answer unexpected queries about the data. Pivot charts add illustrations to the summary data in a PivotTable, allowing the researchers to observe comparisons, patterns, and trends more quickly. Numeric data subtotaling and grouping, data summarization by categories and subcategories, and custom computations and formulas are all possible when using Pivot table.

The questionnaire that was created for this study was adapted from Al-Ababneh (2016). The researchers will gather reviews regarding their satisfaction towards the Hotel Luna which is composed of the 5 dimensions of SERVQUAL. The

researchers will measure the data using a 5-point Likert scale, an interval measurement scale used to analyze the data. A Likert scale is a type of scale that allows people to express themselves in a variety of ways which includes their sentiments or attitudes toward a certain subject (Nemoto & Beglar 2014), where 1 which means “very dissatisfied” and 5 which means “very satisfied”.

Lastly, construct validity will be used to validate the research which will be done by the research adviser. Basically, construct validity refers to a measurement device's general reliability. It must answer the questions: Does the instrument measure the construct that is needed to measure? Does the test relate to the underlying theoretical concept? (Coulacoglou et al., 2017).

Moreover, the researchers forwarded a consent letter to the management regarding the research study which is relevant to Hotel Luna. On the process of getting information that will be provided by TripAdvisor and Agoda's review section, the researchers will guarantee that the identity of the reviewers will remain anonymous and that no harm will be done. Therefore, the Data Privacy Act of 2012 will not be violated because the reviews from the selected online travel agencies was made public.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The focus of this section is to present the results and discussions from the reviews on Hotel Luna using the selected online travel agencies. The reviews were done to have an understanding on how to analyze the reviews on customer satisfaction of Hotel Luna, Vigan City using SERVQUAL Theory. The importance of online reviews and how the guests conduct their own experiences. The study will be using Qualitative Analysis will be used utilizing accessible to the public resources such as the reviews from the selected online travel agencies.

The analysis on Hotel Luna, Vigan City produced 720 reviews which were grouped into five categories. Among the categories are Tangibility, Responsiveness, Empathy, Assurance, and Reliability. The researchers used fivepoint likert scale starting from very dissatisfied (1) to very satisfied (5).

Presentation of Results and Discussions for Qualitative Data

There are various techniques of qualitative data analysis. One of these ways is sentiment analysis, however only few researchers have employed it in their research. Sentiment analysis is the process of extracting relevant subjective information from text using natural language processing and text analysis techniques (MohamedHussein, 2018).

During our time, the use of online travel agency is very popular. Thus, online reviews are also very useful for guests before traveling. This became one of the reasons for analyzing this research. The data was manually entered and categorized using sentiment analysis.

The first area that was examined was the quality of the hotel. The respondents mentioned good quality equipment and approachable staffs. As the review from 2021 said:

“The ambiance of the hotel is very elegant and classy, and I enjoyed the food and services. The staffs and employees are very accommodating and approachable, overall, it was a very good experience, and I will definitely go back in this hotel.”

At this time, the key to competitive market success is giving high-quality service, which will boost consumer happiness. As a result, under the hotel industry, consumer feedback on service quality is critical to the growth of the firm (Ali, 2021). Most of the reviews mentioned good comments regarding the hotel's services and the quality of their equipment. To please its customers and gain their loyalty, hotels should provide a competitive service (Abdulla et al. 2017). Service quality is a strategy for improving the hotel's performance, competitiveness, and adaptability. It's a strategy for ensuring complete guest satisfaction (Abdullah & Abdul Rahman, 2015).

The next area that was examined were the overall look of the hotel. The museum like hotel were examined in the areas of artworks and designs. As the reviews from 2021 said:

“The rooms, dining, and the museum are so beautiful, I love the details, vibes, and design of the hotel especially the museum that has amazing artworks by Filipino and National Artists. The staffs are very welcoming and attentive. We had experienced great service! Highly recommended.”

“Super ok ng customer service 24 hours yung reception, clean rooms and napaka okay ng interiors and museum-like hotel nila. Special shoutout to Chenli and Geffen of the bar area who made our stay super memorable and fun.”

The importance of hotel interior design in influencing consumer perceptions, providing a sense of value, gathering symbolic meanings, and shaping the whole experience is essential. Hotel design is directly connected to the development and transmission of messages and meanings to visitors; all of this points to the importance of design as a marketing segmentation tool and for developing a unique brand in this highly competitive industry (Kontic, 2018). The reviews mentioned the design of the hotel which shows their museum side is also a good impression for guests because of the meaning behind every artwork that reflects to the guest’s experience.

Alongside good or positive reviews, negative reviews are also present. The unexpected comment from 2018 mentioned:

“The towels had blood stains while the bedsheet was also stained. We were instead offered room 401 and we accepted only to discover later that the carpet smelled much worse, it was damp and moldy. Two electrical sockets were not working while two others were burnt, tv turns on by itself, minibar cooler was not working. The pool was also moldy.”

Numerous studies have indicated that smell correlated with revenue, as well as major effects on human emotions and behavior (Yu, 2018). The practice on good hygiene must be prioritized in every hotel. The application of good hygiene practices GMPs are also essential to maintain food safety and quality. Ensure that clients are not exposed to any food-borne illnesses. These processes are a series of procedures designed to achieve specified product identity and/or quality standards services in the culinary business, such as supplies and utensils items may come into contact (Rodrigues et al., 2017).

The researchers used the concept of Internal Analysis using the Strength-Weakness Table. So, we can present the data in this manner.

The five areas were thoroughly analyzed using a Strength-Weakness (SW) Table as shown in Table 2.

The overall performance of Hotel Luna was good. Although the room section of the hotel could use some improvement. Hotel guests' behaviors, interests, and expectations are rapidly changing. Repeat business, word-of-mouth referrals, and good social media reviews will be rewarded for properties that can create a memorable experience through unique features, personal touches, and exceptional customer service (Amadeus Hospitality, 2022). Some of the staffs also need some improvement because some of them treat the guests impolitely. The employees the hotel manage are in charge of looking after guests and giving them a pleasant experience. The level of engagement from guests will improve if the hotel’s personnel is bright and motivated, and their attitude will adjust to reflect who is serving them (SiteMinder, 2022).

Table 2: Internal Analysis of the reviews from selected online travel agencies on Hotel Luna, Vigan City

Area	Strengths	Weaknesses
Tangibility	The hotel rooms and swimming pool are clean, spacious, ornately decorated. It is clean and well maintained. It also has vintage-looking interior and exterior.	The rooms were very small, only few people can accommodate in the pool area. Rooms were a bit dark and no external window and some of the rooms were bad smelling.
Empathy	The staff accommodates the wants and needs of the guests.	The staffs were impolite by taking the needs of the guests.
Reliability	The staffs of the hotel were able to handle the complaints of each customer.	Some staffs were not able to accomplish all the tasks that were given to them by the guests.
Assurance	The staffs were friendly, approachable, and hospitable. Guests were greeted with a smile from each staff.	The guests felt ignored by the staffs and also felt like the guests were talking bad about them by the staffs using different language.
Responsiveness	The staffs are always ready to assist the guests.	The receiving staffs were rude.

Figure 2.

Summary of the results of reviews in Hotel Luna

The summary of the results as shown in Figure 1 using pie chart revealed the reviews of Hotel Luna, Vigan City from the selected online travel agency. According to pie chart in response to Very Satisfied reviews it was building trust towards Hotel Luna's customer service, facilities, amenities, safety, and price, a large portion of respondents are 72% total of 518 reviews. 3% of the guest having not strongly marked or positive characteristics features of Hotel Luna. 25% of the customers are Very Dissatisfied by Hotel Luna, about their poor customer service, facilities, and cleanliness. This demonstrates the significance of online reviews. Only by providing dependable and high-quality service and making consumers happy can a company earn favorable feedback, Positive feedback and promotes trust. Negative evaluations, on the other hand, might be advantageous to businesses. They expose a company's defects in order to correct them, which is essential for its growth and development.

5. CONCLUSION

The intention of this chapter is to determine whether the study's objectives were fulfilled. As a result, this section will begin with a conclusion and end with recommendations. The objective of this research is to analyze the reviews on customer satisfaction in the Hotel Luna, Vigan City based on the SERVQUAL Theory in terms of: Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy, and Responsiveness in order to create a recommendation for the hotel. Based on the sentimental analysis, it shows that the research objective was achieved since the data was analyzed and sorted, while the major categories were also recognized.

The satisfaction based on the SERVQUAL questionnaires result of guests that stayed in Hotel Luna, Vigan City are satisfied. The guests were particularly pleased with the Hotel Luna's ability to provide high-quality service. In this study, the variables: Responsiveness, Tangibility and Assurance received the highest percentage for satisfied reviews. On the other hand, Empathy and Reliability received low percentage for satisfied reviews. Most of the guests mentioned the classic interior design of the hotel. Aside from it being an accommodation, it is also a museum so the guests were also entertained and gained new knowledge because of Hotel Luna.

As a result, the findings of this study may be valuable to hotel management in terms of improving or maintaining the hotel's performance and image. With the help of the research recommendation, hotel management may also investigate the major reasons for unfavorable reasons that contributed to dissatisfied guests and enhance their service. Satisfaction has been shown to be deeply involved to guests' intention to revisit the hotel, making it a necessary condition of loyalty. When the service quality improved, not only does customer happiness increase, but so does the guests' value, which has a stronger influence on the intention to revisit. These things can be taken into consideration for the betterment/recommendation of the hotel:

- Since empathy was shown to be one of the weakest variable, the hotel management should therefore conduct empathy education in order for the employees to improve their communication skills and be prepared to sympathize.
- Reliability was also shown to be one of the weakest variable, therefore the hotel management must give high-quality training and development opportunities; unfortunately, this takes time and money, but it is well worth the effort.
- Tangibility was shown to be the strongest variable. The hotel management must maintain or improve the beauty of their external appearance and facilities since it will be one of their strongest point for guests to revisit them in the future. This study is limited in its ability to having no demographic characteristics of respondents since it is from online reviews. Understanding the demographic characteristics of the participants helps to put the data collected into context.

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